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US POLICY TOWARDS DETERMINING TRANSPORT ROUTES OF CASPIAN BASIN OIL AND GAS RESOURCES

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Abstract

One of the factors that increases the geopolitical importance of the Caspian basin is its location at the intersection of energy transmission lines and east-west and north-south transport corridors. In the article, the interests of the United States, which is considered the world's superpower, in determining the export routes of the energy resources of the Caspian Sea are extensively analyzed. In the first sub-heading, the policy followed by the USA in the field of defining energy transport routes within the scope of its geo-economic interests in the Caspian Basin is analyzed. In the second sub-heading, the policy carried out by the official Washington in determining the direct export oil pipelines of the region was investigated. The essence of the policy of the White House in this direction is to achieve the construction of export pipelines by bypassing Russia and Iran as much as possible, to serve the energy security of its allies, and to ensure the participation of US countries in those projects.

Keywords: USA, Caspian basin, oil and gas, pipeline, energy security.

One of the states with a special interest in the Caspian Basin is the United States. J.J. Mearsheimer, a professor of political science at the University of Chicago, argued that after the end of the Cold War, the main goal of the United States was to dominate the Western Hemisphere and prevent another state from becoming the sole ruler in the other hemisphere [1, 3]. In this regard, the United States entered into a power struggle with Russia and China, which had the potential to emerge as a planetary rival in the Caspian Basin. It is possible to divide the United States' policy towards the region into the periods from the collapse of the USSR to the mid-1990s, from the mid-1990s to the events of July 11, 2001, and from 2001 to the present. In the first stage, the United States provided economic and financial assistance to the states of the region, liberalizing the centralized and largely state-monopolized economy formed during the Soviet regime, and providing financial and other assistance in carrying out reforms to establish a market-oriented economy. The goal was to achieve US investment in the rich underground and surface resources of the region and to ensure the protection of these investments through laws adopted by the state. In the first stage, the US also wanted to achieve the neutralization of the remnants of nuclear weapons left over from the Soviet era, as well as chemical weapons, especially in Kazakhstan and partly in Uzbekistan. If we recall that the region in question is a direct border with countries such as Afghanistan and Pakistan, where terrorist groups operate extensively, and Iran, the most important competitor of the US in the Near and Middle East, also has a long land border with the region, then it is not difficult to understand the US concern.

1. The importance of the Caspian Basin for the US from a geopolitical and geoeconomic perspective In the early 90s of the 20th century, a new direction of US foreign policy activity called the "Caspian region policy" was determined. In the face of the planet's growing energy needs and the need to expand trade relations, the Caspian basin has become a crossroads of geoeconomic

interests, attracting the attention of the entire transnational world with its rich hydrocarbon resources, East-West, North-South connections, and opportunities in the field of transport and communication. As the newspaper "Fyneshill Times" wrote in the mid-90s of the last century, the United States has focused its main efforts on creating an American sphere of influence in the Caucasus and the Caspian in order to gain control over oil and on Caspian oil [7]. Since the United States did not have the opportunity to actively intervene in the post-Soviet space at that time, it set itself the geopolitical task of determining the boundaries of the spread of Russian influence in three crucial directions: from Ukraine to the Balkans, from Azerbaijan to the South Caucasus, and from Kazakhstan to Central Asia, and chose Ukraine, Azerbaijan, and Kazakhstan as three favorite countries for official Washington. It should be borne in mind that the last two directions are directly related to the Caspian region [2, 29-30]. Z. Brzezinski in his work "The Grand Chessboard" stated that the United States should first support Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan in the Caspian basin to leave Russia's orbit, and that achieving Georgia's independent policy would create conditions for the transportation of energy resources to the west. According to Brzezinski, the independent energy policy of Kazakhstan and Azerbaijan would have greatly influenced the position of Turkmenistan, which is rich in hydrocarbon resources [3, 174-181].

In 1994, by order of US President B. Clinton, a Special Working Group was established to deal with the Caspian policy of official Washington. The Special Working Group included quite influential state bodies and their leading representatives [12, 152], which indicates the importance of the region for the US. According to the Special Working Group, the energy resources of the Caspian Sea could reduce the US dependence on energy sources in the Middle East in the near future. Some details of the US policy towards the region were outlined in the report "Energy Development of the Caspian Basin" prepared by the State Department in 1997.

It shows; The growth and expansion of world energy supply as an addition to the Iranian Gulf, as well as the exploitation of the energy resources of the Caspian Basin in order to insure the energy interests of the West here; Limiting the income of this country for the sake of "isolation of Iran", and to achieve this goal, keeping Iran out of the development and transportation of Caspian energy resources as much as possible, etc.

In 1998, the position of Special Advisor to the US President on the Caspian Sea was established. R. Morningstar, a well-known expert on energy issues and later the US ambassador to Azerbaijan, was appointed to this post. This in itself once again proves that the region has entered the sphere of special interest of the US.

However, since Russia considers the Caspian region to be its "backyard", it is of great strategic importance for this country, and official Moscow did not want to cede its say here to the US. The most pragmatic ways for the US to establish itself in the region could be "pipeline diplomacy" supported by Europe.

The director of the Russian Center for Strategic Studies, A. Gusher, indicates that the United States has three main interests in the Caspian region: commercial interest, energy interest, and geopolitical interest. Commenting on geopolitical interest, A. Gusher states that currently the United States' participation in the development of Caspian oil projects has more geopolitical significance than economic. The author draws attention to the geography of the Caspian Sea and shows that this water basin is located in the triangle of the geopolitical and military rivals of the United States in the global space, Russia, China, and Iran [14, 17; 18, 28]. Control over the Caspian Sea allows the United States to achieve global hegemony in five seas (the Black Sea, the Mediterranean Sea, the Caspian Sea, the Persian Gulf, and the Arabian Sea) and the entire continent. In addition, the location in the Caspian Sea could play a role in preventing Russia from showing its muscle to the former Soviet republics whose economies were still fragile, and in preventing those states from taking a stand against the expansion of Russian expansionist policies. The policy of a state like the United States in the region is aimed at capturing strategic positions rather than realizing economic interests. In such a political approach, which reflects the geostrategic tactics of the United States, all possible means were used to achieve control over the resources of the Caspian Sea and attract the region to the West. Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan were dependent on the Russian pipeline system in terms of energy resource exports, which was used by official Moscow as a means of political pressure. The United States, while supporting the construction of diversified pipelines, wants to put an end to Russia's hegemony in this area. In this way, it is trying to achieve a more reliable energy supply for itself and its allies in Europe. In our opinion, the strengthening of the United States in the region is also aimed at preventing the expansion of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), which Russia and China want to form and which is predicted to act as an alternative to NATO.

Important directions of the US policy regarding the Caspian Sea basin are reflected in another state document. Thus, this issue was included in the resolution

adopted by the Congress in November 1997 on the policy towards the countries of the Caucasus and Central Asia. The resolution included the issues of assisting in the development of the necessary infrastructure for the transport, communications and energy sectors, as well as the West-East trade corridor, thereby strengthening the internal relations and commercial ties of these countries with each other and with the countries of the Euro-Atlantic alliance, where stable, democratic, free market economies prevail [14, 17; 18, 29]. As can be seen from the document, part of the US interests in the region is the expansion of the region's transport and communications infrastructure and having a certain control over it. In this regard, the restoration of the historical "Silk Road" is beneficial for this superpower.

The US policy towards the Caspian region is marked by three main red lines: 1. Preventing Russia from taking the region under its influence, 2. Preventing Iran from strengthening its position in the region by spreading radical Islam, 3. Establishing more reliable economic and trade cooperation by achieving the development of human rights and democracy [19]. Although the greatest power struggle in the region is between the US and Russia, it has recently been seen that this has shifted between Washington and Beijing. The US is disturbed by Russia's insistence on transporting the rich hydrocarbon resources of the Caspian republics (Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan and Azerbaijan) to world markets only through Russian territory, as it did during the former Soviet era. It should be noted that the existing pipeline system in the Caspian countries dates back to the Soviet era and its technical indicators are not satisfactory.

2. The US policy towards determining the routes for transporting energy resources in the region.

The US, as a superpower, is interested in transporting the region's energy resources through a diversified pipeline system bypassing Russia. According to N.A. Nartov, one of the famous Russian geopoliticians, the US desire to strengthen itself in the western Caspian region was first of all calculated to squeeze Russia out of the region and achieve the transportation of energy resources outside the control of official Moscow and Tehran [16, 163-164].

Against the background of a number of government changes in the US, support for a project by various political circles and continuous participation in it has been a truly remarkable phenomenon. Nevertheless, BTC is the largest project that the US has supported, developed and strategically assisted in the implementation of the former Soviet Union during the three different US governments.

By defending a diversified pipeline system, the United States pursues the following goals: to support the territorial integrity and development of the regional states, to strengthen their independence and support the transition to a market economy, to expand the trade activities of US companies in this region, to ensure energy security, etc. [4, 55].

The struggle of the United States to maintain its sovereignty over the international system is organized

by the protection of economic power, which has become the most important element of national power today. Economic strategy is considered a priority of modern US foreign policy. In 1990-2000, the US economy grew by 27%. The US share in the world market increased from 25.9% to 31.2% between 1996-2002 [20, 38; 18, 22]. In order to maintain its economic sovereignty and not to cede the title of superpower to other states, the United States is targeting the control of energy resources, which are the "soul" of the economy. In this context, under the instructions of President George W. Bush, the National Energy Policy Development Group (NEPDG) prepared a report in May 2001 that explained the position and policies of the United States in the energy sector over the next 20 years and formed the basis for the work being done in this direction. According to this report, if the energy production rate between 1990 and 2000 follows the same statistics in subsequent years, the United States will remain insufficient to meet its energy consumption and its energy needs will increase. This situation has caused concern that it will deeply undermine the US economy.

The United States is the world's third largest oil producer (after Saudi Arabia and the Russian Federation) and the world's largest oil consumer. Oil is the most widely used energy source in the United States with 39%, and it is predicted that oil will continue to be the leading source of consumption in the future.

The United States ranks third in the world with 8.69 billion barrels of oil production per day. It should be noted that the first two places are occupied by Saudi Arabia and the Russian Federation. There is a negative balance between oil production and consumption in the United States. Thus, as we have shown above, while daily oil production was 8.69 billion barrels, consumption was 20.5 billion barrels. By the way, it should be noted that with this indicator, the United States surpasses its closest follower China (8.69 billion barrels) by about 2.5 times. Official Washington ranks 6th in the world with 189 trillion cubic feet of natural gas reserves [5].

The United States exports oil mainly to Canada, Mexico, Venezuela, Saudi Arabia and the Middle East countries full of conflicts are doing it. After the end of the Cold War, the US, in order to maintain its title as the world's superpower, needed to meet not only its own energy needs, but also the energy needs of its allies with whom its economy is closely connected. Ensuring energy security is a key issue for official Washington in order to become a world superpower. This is also dictated by the fact that the US is the world's largest oil importer, which in turn dictates that such a situation first of all dictates ensuring source diversity. It is precisely because of the importance given to source diversity that the US exports oil from more than 60 countries. Naturally, countries that import oil become the sphere of interest of official Washington. Despite the priority of oil in energy consumption, the country's liquid fuel reserves are rapidly decreasing, and thus the US's dependence on foreign oil is increasing every passing day. While the US dependence on imported oil was 56% in 2000, this indicator was over 60% in 2010 [8, 92-93].

The following are the possible priority market areas for the next 25 years in order to meet the growing energy needs of the US:

- Russia-East Siberia
- Caspian Basin
- West Africa

It should be noted that in October 1998, the US Secretary of Energy, together with the heads of state of Azerbaijan, Georgia, Turkey, Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan, signed a declaration calling for the approval of BTC as a major export pipeline [6, 322; 15, 322], which once again confirms the interest of official Washington in the project. Following this, the geopolitical and geostrategic importance of BTC was substantiated in a meeting held at the White House with the heads of US oil companies. The presence of President Clinton at the signing ceremony of the Istanbul Declaration (1999) confirms the above. It is more clear that the US had two specific interests in the BTC project. First, the implementation of this project would further strengthen the independence of Azerbaijan and Georgia and reduce Russia's influence in the region. Second, an alternative source of oil to the Persian Gulf would be achieved.

The head of the Russian Institute of Global Problems, M. Delyagin, evaluates BTC as a project implemented by the United States in order to strategically tear the Caucasus away from Russia. According to the author, the economic development of the newly independent republics in the South Caucasus is narrowing Russia's influence over the region [13, 73-74]

From an economic and geographical point of view, the transportation of Caspian hydrocarbon resources through the Persian Gulf seemed more beneficial. The United States opposes the transportation of Caspian liquid and blue fuel through Iranian territory and tries to suppress all initiatives in this direction. Due to the well-known crisis between our southern neighbor and the United States and the West in general, bypassing Iran is a red line in the policy pursued by official Washington in the export of oil and gas resources of the region. Iran's proximity to the Caspian countries in historical, cultural, religious and geographical terms and its desire to increase its influence in the region by taking advantage of these advantages are met with sharp reactions from the United States. The US still supports the TAPI (Turkmenistan, Afghanistan, Pakistan and India) project, which bypasses Iran in transporting Caspian energy resources to the south.

Ensuring the participation of US companies in newly established pipeline consortia is also an integral part of Washington's political course. [11, 5]

Based on the opinions of experts in international relations and geopolitics, as well as our research, we can conclude that fierce competition for the extraction and export of Caspian oil and gas resources will continue in the coming decades.

Conclusion: The US is trying to prevent its EU allies from becoming more dependent on Russia to meet their rapidly growing energy needs. This would both prevent Russia from strengthening its influence in Europe, and on the other hand, the ability of the Cas-

pian littoral states of Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan to pursue an independent energy export policy could significantly improve their economic situation. This would undoubtedly lead to the strengthening of the economic and political positions of these newly independent states and would significantly distance them from Moscow's orbit. Integration into the West would create broad opportunities for the activities of US companies by giving impetus to the formation of a liberal economy.

The US, in addition to not wanting the transportation of Caspian hydrocarbon resources through Russia, was also opposed to their transportation through Iranian territory. The construction of a pipeline system directed towards China (the other being Russia), one of its two main rivals in the region, is also not in line with the interests of official Washington.

The US interests in the construction of a pipeline system in the Caspian basin that is more diversified towards the West can be grouped as follows. A) The construction of a pipeline system outside the control of Russia and Iran will help the newly independent Caspian republics to strengthen their economies and politics

B) The role that the pipeline will play in the energy security of the US allies in the region by passing through Turkey

C) US business interests - ensuring the participation of US companies in new projects

D) Supporting democratic processes in the region.

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